

IR58025A/IR21567. But the last two hybrids also possess long slender and attractive grains, moderate HR, and a high VER, a good combination of quality traits. ■

Studying comparative suitability of CMS lines

M. I. Ahmed, S. Singh, B. C. Viraktamath, M. S. Ramesha, and C. H. M. Vijayakumar, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Parental lines constitute the first and foremost step in a hybrid breeding program. In this context, developing a commercially viable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line is considered to be a highly cumbersome process. In fact, the belated success of hybrid rice technology in India was basically due to the nonavailability of a CMS line suited to the tropics. Over the years, a large number of male sterile lines with different cyto sterility sources have been developed in India and elsewhere. Only a few—such as IR58025A and IR62829A—are now used commercially in India. They possess all the essential traits—complete and stable male sterility, high outcrossing rate, better grain quality, easy restorability, good combining ability, and adaptability—of a commercially viable CMS line. Some 64 CMS lines from India, China, Malaysia, and IRRI were evaluated along with IR58025A, IR62829A, and standard checks in the wet season of 1995 and 1996 and dry season of 1994 and 1995 to assess their comparative suitability for commercial use. The CMS lines, along with their corresponding maintainers, were grown for maintenance and evaluation for their floral traits such as pollen sterility, panicle and stigma exertion, outcrossing rate, duration and angle of glume opening, growth duration, number of effective tillers, spikelets panicle⁻¹, grain type, adaptability, and pigmentation (if any). Each CMS line was characterized for all the traits individually. The final value was

obtained by adding together the weighted score allotted to a CMS line for all these traits. This single final value on a 1 to 9 scale indicated the line's practical utility.

Only 11 lines were found to be equally better for all the characters studied than IR58025A and IR62829A: four CMS lines (IR68280A, IR68897A, IR68899A, and IR69628A) from IRRI, two (DRR2A and DRR3A) from the Directorate of Rice Research, and one each from China (9601A), Malaysia (MH-841A), IARI (Pusa 5A), Cuttack (CRMS 31A), and Faizabad (NDCMS 7A). Some of the promising CMS lines were IR67684A, IR68890A, IR68902A, IR68279A, IR68895A, and CRMS 6A. About 31 lines possess one or two good characters and can be used for specific purposes. All Chinese lines, for example, are useful as cyto sterility sources to convert promising maintainers into new CMS lines. The remaining 16 lines have one or more drawbacks and will need further improvement. The promising CMS lines are now being studied for their combining ability and use in breeding programs. ■

Identifying a new long-duration CMS line (APMS 5A) for coastal regions

R. V. Kumar, P. V. Satyanarayana, and M. S. Rao, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru 534122, India

Several male sterile lines developed in India belong to the early- to medium-duration group. Hybrids developed using these male sterile lines are also of early to medium growth duration. These hybrids are not suitable for cultivation during the wet season, particularly in the coastal areas of Andhra Pradesh, where long-duration varieties are predominantly grown. We need to develop long-duration rice hybrids to increase rice productivity and fit them into the cropping system. An effort was made to develop long-duration (145-150 d) and stable local

cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines. Several testcrosses were made using local long-duration elite lines and IRRI CMS lines to screen the elite varieties for their maintaining or restoring ability. A few long-duration maintainer lines were identified based on pollen and spikelet sterility. MTU4870 was therefore selected and successfully converted into a local cyto sterile line in the background of a wild abortive source of cytoplasm through the backcross breeding technique. This line was designated as APMS5A.

APMS5A is a long-duration (145-150 d) line with tolerance for brown planthopper, bacterial leaf blight, rice tungro virus, and sheath blight. It also possesses a sturdy culm. It has a comparable angle of spikelet opening duration (190 min), angle of spikelet opening (31°C), stigma exertion, and natural outcrossing potential (12%) with the popular CMS line IR58025A. APMS5A, a 100% sterile line, is the first long-duration CMS line developed in India with desirable floral and agronomic traits. A few effective restorers were also identified. APMS5A will facilitate the development of long-duration rice hybrids suitable for cultivation in the coastal areas. ■

Wide hybridization for diversification of CMS in rice

N. T. Hoan, N. P. Sarma, and E. A. Siddiq, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

To identify new sources of male sterility-inducing cytoplasm within the A genome of genus *Oryza*, 132 inter-specific crosses involving accessions of four wild (*O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara*, *O. barthii*, and *O. longistaminata*) and two cultivated species (*O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima*) were effected. Accessions possessing sterility-inducing cytoplasm were identified following reciprocal and F₂ backcross methods and advanced through substitution backcrossing to develop cytoplasmic

male sterile (CMS) lines. Two indices were used: (1) pollen morphology and staining pattern and (2) type of interaction with a set of maintainers and restorers of wild abortive (WA) cyto sterile stock. The newly developed CMS lines are grouped using these indices as follows: I. RPMS1 (*O. rufipogon*; VNI) and RPMS2 (*O. nivara*; DRW21039) are gametophytic types; II. RPMS3 (*O. nivara*; DRW21030) is similar to MS577A in pollen stainability, but the restoration and maintenance reactions are similar to those of

the WA type; III. RPMS4 (*O. nivara*; DRW21018) is a sporophytic type, but restorers and maintainers are different from WA; IV. RPMS5 and RPMS6 (*O. nivara*; RPW21111) are sporophytic types with restorer and maintainer reactions similar to those of WA. All the new CMS lines possessed complete panicle exertion essential for enhancing outcrossed seed yield.

For the two stable CMS lines, MS577A and IR66707A, no restorers are available in cultivated rice germplasm. A search for restorer sources for these

CMS lines was made among the wild accessions of the A genome species. Although none of the accessions could restore fertility in IR66707A, three accessions of *O. rufipogon* (VN2, DRW22016, DRW220175) and one each from *O. sativa* f. *spontanea* (RPW20001) and *O. glaberrima* (DRGL 30090) did restore fertility in MS577A. Studies on the genetics of fertility restoration in these cross combinations indicated that two dominant genes act in an additive manner to restore fertility. ■

Krishna CMS lines in the background of four different cytoplasmic sources in rice

S. B. Pradhan and P. J. Jachuck, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Four cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines of Krishna with sterile cytoplasm from four different sources (wild abortive [WA], *O. perennis*, Kalinga 1, and Lalruma from Mizoram) have been developed. The two CMS lines—Krishna A with WA and Krishna A with *O. perennis* as a source—were developed through conversion with CMS lines V20A (WA) and IR66707A (*O. perennis*), respectively, by subsequent backcrossing with common isonuclear main-

tainer Krishna A. But Krishna A with Kalinga 1 and Krishna A with Lalruma cytoplasmic sources were developed through indica / indica crosses. These four CMS lines are all dwarf in stature, are of medium duration, and have reduced white anthers that exhibit 80-90% unstained withered pollen grains.

To understand the nature of these four cyto sterility sources, they were testcrossed with four maintainers—V20B (maintainer of WA), IR66707B (maintainer of *O. perennis*), Yar-Ai-ZhaoB (maintainer of Gambiaca), and MS577B (maintainer of *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*)—and the elite inbred lines SPR7210-1-3, IR48725-B-B-120-1, NDR30074, TTB150-61, and R657-93-869. The sterility of the four CMS lines was maintained by the four main-

tainers. The restorer SPR7210-1-3 of Krishna A (WA) was found to be a maintainer of the other three CMS lines—Krishna A (*O. perennis*), Krishna A (Kalinga 1), and Krishna A (Lalruma)—whereas the restorer IR48725-B-B-120-1 of Krishna A (WA) behaved as partial restorer of Krishna A (Kalinga 1) and Krishna A (Lalruma) and as a maintainer of Krishna A (*O. perennis*). Variety R657-93-869 was found to be a partial restorer of Krishna A (WA) and Krishna A (Lalruma) and a maintainer of Krishna A (Kalinga 1) and Krishna A (*O. perennis*). The restorer TTB150-61 for Krishna A (Lalruma) behaved as a partial restorer of Krishna A (WA) and Krishna A (Kalinga 1), and as a maintainer of Krishna A (*O. perennis*). ■

Characterizing thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines of rice

B. C. Viraktamath, M. T. Lopez, and S. S. Virmani, IRRI

The cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) system is widely used to develop rice hybrids. Although effective, this system is quite cumbersome to practice. Certain genic male sterile lines that revert to fertility under specific temperature are called thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines. Deployment of the TGMS system to develop two-line hybrids has several

advantages over the conventional CMS system, as it requires neither maintainers for seed multiplication nor restorers for producing hybrids. In addition, two-line hybrids may not suffer from possible negative effects of the sterility-inducing cytoplasm. For an effective use of TGMS lines, they have to be characterized for their critical sterility and fertility points. This information is essential for deciding on a suitable location and / or period for seed multiplication and hybrid seed production. Two IRRI-bred indica TGMS lines-IR68945-4-33-4-14 and IR68949-11-5-31-along with their japonica TGMS donor, were charac-

terized under controlled conditions in the IRRI phytotron. These lines were subjected to eight constant temperatures (20-32 °C) and four day-night combination temperatures (27 / 21 °C-32 / 24 °C) for a period of 3 wk during the sensitive stage. The critical sterility point for both lines was 30 °C and above, whereas it was only 27 °C and above for Norin PL 12. The critical fertility points for the indica TGMS lines ranged between 24-28 °C (constant temperate) and 27 / 21 °C-28 / 22 °C (day-night combination temperature). Norin PL 12 was found to be very sensitive to higher temperature compared with the indica TGMS lines.